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A PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF REPETITIONS IN TURKISH SPEECH: INFLUENCE OF SPEECH CONDITION

***Психолінгвістичний аналіз повторень в турецькій мові:
вплив мовного стану***

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Abstract

This paper addresses the influence of speech condition on fluent Turkish native speakers' repetition type of speech disfluency production rates. Totally 70 participants from three different age groups (18-27, 33-50 and over 50) took part in the study. 33-50 and over 50-year-olds were divided into two subgroups according to their educational levels. Gender distribution was equal in each group. Prepared and unprepared speech samples consisting of at least 300 words for each participant were gathered by conducting face-to-face interviews, and each repetition was marked on the transcriptions of the interviews by hand. As a result, all 33–50-year-old participants produced more repetitions in prepared speech condition compared to unprepared speech condition. Regarding gender and educational level variables, all 33–50-year-old female participants, and over-50-year-old female professors produced more repetitions in prepared speech condition than unprepared speech condition.

Keywords: *psycholinguistics, speech production, educational background, turkish speech, repetitions.*

Introduction

Repetition, which is a type of disfluency interrupting the flow of speech, has been described and classified by different researchers in various ways in the related literature.

MacClay & Osgood (1959) emphasize that repetition type of disfluencies cover all repetitions from the length of a phoneme to several words.

Clark & Wasow (1998: 201) suggest that speakers often repeat the first word of major constituents, as in, “I uh I wouldn’t be surprised at that”. Repeats like this divide into four stages: an initial commitment to the constituent (with “I”); the suspension of speech; a hiatus in speaking (filled with “uh”); and a restart of the constituent (“I wouldn’t...”). They also point out that repeating a word is often viewed as an error, but it should also be considered as a solution to the problems regarding how to speak in a timely fashion and yet how to speak smoothly.

Repetitions were also considered as a stuttering signal unlike most other types of disfluency. Johnson (1961: 3–4) categorizes repetitions as part-word repetitions (syllables and sounds), word repetitions, and phrase repetitions.

Hieke (1981: 152) divides repetitions into two different categories as retrospective and prospective repetitions and states that: “*Prospective repeats are anticipatory and serve as a device to gain time. Retrospective repeats, on the other hand, while also associated with a lexical search at times, perform primarily a bridging function to prior speech segments which have become separated from the rest through intervening time (due to pauses and other hesitations). Rather than serving a stalling function, as a rule they do just the opposite in that they rectify breaks in production by assuring that the last segment before the break is now repeated, and fluency thus reestablished*”. The results of the research conducted by Shriberg (1995) on the acoustic properties of repetitions in the following years also supported Hieke’s (1981) retrospective and prospective categorization of repetitions.

Methods and Techniques of the Research

Repetition disfluency data was gathered from the conversations which had been recorded and transcribed. Five age groups were constructed from Turkish native speakers aged between 18-23 (14 participants), 33-50 (two-sub groups with different education levels – 28 participants), and who were over 50-year-olds (two-sub groups with different education levels – 28 participants). Speech samples of at least 300 words from each participant both in the prepared and unprepared speech conditions were gathered by conducting face-to-face interviews. In prepared speech condition, participants answered the questions that they had seen before the interviews, so they could plan their speech. In the unprepared speech condition, they answered the questions they had not seen before spontaneously. The questions that were asked

during the interviews were about general topics such as, work, hobbies, career, giving directions, or cooking instructions. All repetitions were marked by hand in the transcript. The repetition rates of the speakers were calculated by taking an average of repetitions in every 100 words. The gathered data was analyzed according to speech condition (prepared/unprepared) variable.

Results

3.1. Evaluation of Repetition Data According to Speech Condition (Prepared / Unprepared) v Variable

The differences among the speech disfluency rates of the participants with different educational levels in prepared and unprepared speech conditions were analyzed with the Mann-Whitney U Test.

3.1.1. An Analysis of “Repetition” Type of Disfluencies According to Speech Condition Variable (Prepared / Unprepared) Independent of Gender and Education Level Variables

Repetition rates of the participants in the age groups of 18–23, 33–50, and over 50 according to speech condition variable, independent of gender and education level variables, are as shown in Table 1:

Table 1. *Repetition Rates in Prepared and Unprepared Speech According to Speech Condition Variable*

Age	REPETITIONS			
	Prepared Speech		Unprepared Speech	
	Mean± SD	Median (Min_Max)	Mean±SD	Median (Min_Max)
18-23-Year-Olds n=14	0.14±0.31	0.00 (0-1.63)	0.10±0.17	0 (0-0.49)
33-50-Year-Olds n=28	0.25±0.44	0.11 (0-2.22)	0.16±0.37	0 (0-1.84)
Over 50-Year-Olds n=28	0.27±0.34	0.20 (0-1.26)	0.21±0.31	0.09 (0-1.23)
P	0.153		0,000***	

Mean; Arithmetic mean, SD; Standard deviation

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

As shown in Table 1, there were not any statistically significant differences among the repetition production rates of 18–23 and over 50-year-olds in the context of the speech condition (prepared/unprepared) variable.

When repetition rates of all 33–50-year-old participants were evaluated by considering only the speech condition variable, regardless of gender and educational background variables, the median for prepared speech is 0.11 (0-2.22) whereas it is 0 (0-1.84) in unprepared speech. The difference is statistically significant ($p=0.03<0.05$). The median in unprepared speech is lower than the median in prepared speech. Consequently, 33–50-year-old participants employ more repetitions in every 100 words in prepared speech compared to unprepared speech. There is no such statistically meaningful difference for the other age groups (18–23, and over 50).

3.1.2. An Analysis of “Repetition” Type of Disfluencies According to Speech Condition Variable (Prepared / Unprepared) by Regarding Gender and Education Level Variables

Repetition rates of the participants from the age groups of 18–23, 33–50, and over 50 according to speech condition variable, regarding gender and education level variables, are as shown in Table 2.

The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was employed to find out whether there were any significant differences between the participants’ prepared and unprepared speech condition fluency assessments in terms of the repetition production rates.

Table 2. *Repetition Rates of Females in Prepared and Unprepared Speech According to Speech Condition*

Age	FEMALE				
	Prepared Speech		Unprepared Speech		p
	Mean± SD	Median (Min_Max)	Mean± SD	Median (Min_Max)	
18-23-Year-Olds	0±0	0	0.03±0.08	0 (0-0.20)	0.31
3-50-Year-Old Elementary/Middle School Graduates	0.23±0.19	0.25 (0-0.60)	0.03±0.05	0 (0-0.12)	0.02*
33-50-Year-Old Bachelor’s-Master’s/ Doctoral Degree Holders	0.15±0.15	0.09 (0-0.39)	0.02±0.04	0.01 (0-0.12)	0.04*
Over 50-Year-Old Elementary/Middle School Graduates	0.14±0.18	0 (0-0.40)	0.35±0.45	0.24 (0-1.23)	0.07
Over 50-Year-Old Professors	0.31±0.35	0.22 (0-1.01)	0.20±0.02	0 (0-0.05)	0.04*

Mean; Arithmetic mean, SD; Standard deviation

* $p<0.05$ ** $p<0.01$ *** $p<0.001$

The repetition median for elementary/middle school graduate females is 0.25 (0-0.60) in planned speech condition whereas it is 0 (0-0.12) in spontaneous speech condition. The difference is statistically significant ($p=0.02<0.05$). The repetition median is lower in unprepared speech condition.

For 33-50-year-old bachelor's-Master's / doctoral degree holder females, the repetition median is 0.09 (0-0.39) in planned speech condition whereas it is 0.01 (0-0.12) in unprepared speech. The difference is statistically significant for this group, too ($p=0.04<0.05$). The repetition median is lower in unprepared speech condition.

There is also a statistically significant difference between two speech conditions in terms of the repetition production rates of over 50-year-old female professors. The median is 0.22 (0-1.01) in prepared speech condition whereas it is 0 (0-0.05) in unprepared speech condition. The difference is meaningful ($p=0.04<0.05$). The repetition median is lower in unprepared speech condition.

Table 3. *Repetition Rates of Males in Prepared and Unprepared Speech According to Speech Condition*

Age	MALE				
	Prepared Speech		Unprepared Speech		p
	Mean±SD	Median (Min_Max)	Mean±SD	Median (Min_Max)	
18-23-Year-Olds	0.23 ± 0.42	0.11 (0-1.16)	0.18±0.20	0.11 (0-0.49)	0.89
3-50-Year-Old Elementary/Middle School Graduates	0.51± 0.81	0.21 (0-2.22)	0.48±0.65	0.33 (0-1.84)	0.60
33-50-Year-Old Bachelor's- Master's/ Doctoral Degree Holders	0.10 ± 0.18	0 (0-0.48)	0.11±0.20	0 (0-0.46)	1.00
Over 50-Year-Old 50 Elementary/Middle School Graduates	0.32 ± 0.46	0.16 (0 -1.26)	0.14±0.11	0.16 (0 -0.27)	0.46
Over 50-Year-Old Professors	0.34 ± 0.35	0.24 (0-0.87)	0.32±0.37	0.15 (0-1.05)	0.75

Mean; Arithmetic mean, SD; Standard deviation

* $p<0.05$ ** $p<0.01$ *** $p<0.001$

As shown in Table 3, there were not any statistically significant differences between two different speech conditions (prepared/unprepared) in terms of the repetition production rates of male participants. The speech condition

(prepared / unprepared) variable was not influential in the production of repetition type of disfluency for males.

Conclusions

According to the statistical analyses of the repetition data in terms of the speech condition variable only (independent of gender and educational background variables):

- 33-50-year-old all participants produced more repetitions in prepared speech condition compared to unprepared speech condition.

When repetition rates were analyzed according to speech condition variable (prepared/unprepared), gender and educational background variables;

- 33-50-year-old all participants and over 50-year-old female professors produced more repetitions in prepared speech condition compared to unprepared speech condition.

In sum; Turkish speakers from three different age groups spoke more fluently in unprepared speech condition in general compared to prepared speech condition in the current study. This finding is interesting since planned speech condition is normally expected to reduce the planning burden which results in less disfluency production. Levelt (1989: 28) states that message generation and monitoring stages of speech production are controlled activities requiring the speaker's continuing attention, but grammatical encoding, form encoding, and articulating phases are automatic to a large degree. Since planning stage is under the control of the speaker, when the control is weakened and distracted, disfluencies become more frequent. As emphasized by Elyıldırım (2005: 4), distractions can be listed as physical and mental fatigue, time distress, and situation-related stress.

As mentioned before, in planned speech condition speakers were asked to prepare their answers by looking at the questions before the interviews. Trying to follow their speech plan in prepared speech condition could probably lead to more stress which resulted in more disfluency production. There are lots of research findings emphasizing the influence of increasing anxiety levels on disfluency production. (Bard, 2001; Carroll, 2008; Christenfeld & Creager, 1996; Harrigan et al., 1994; Mahl, 1987; Mehrabian, 1971).

Hockett (1967: 115) states that “whenever a speaker feels some anxiety about a possible lapse, he will be led to focus attention more than normally on what he has

just said and on what he is just about to say”. The “Vicious Circle Hypothesis” (Vasic & Wijnen, 2001) depends on this idea. According to it, stutterers follow speech production more carefully than normal speakers which increases the rate of the stuttering type of pathological disfluencies. Normal speakers’ following prepared speech more carefully compared to unprepared speech may have influence on the increase of speech disfluencies in prepared speech condition.

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